

THE GENERATIVE COMPOUNDS - ALBANIAN AND ENGLISH

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Abstract:

The generative compound words are all the words that are compounds from two or more words and both of them creative the new words with the new meaning. In this investigation, will be generated some compound words. They are mentioned in the keywords. In linguistics, a compound is a lexeme (less precisely, a word) that consists of more than one stem. Compounding or composition is the word-formation that creates compound lexemes (the other word-formation process being derivation). Compounding or word-compounding refers to the faculty and device of language to form new words by combining or putting together old words. In other words, compound, compounding or word-compounding occurs when a person attaches two or more words together to make them one word. The meanings of the words interrelate in such a way that a new meaning comes out which is very different from the meanings of the isolated original words.

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1. Introduction

The generative studies of the noun phrase and the compound words aren't analyzed as the word-formation and in the function of the sentence between two languages. In this study, some examples will be given, in both Albanian and English languages.

In Albanian language, the compound nouns can generative in this way (*bregdet* and *kryeqytet*):

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The first diagram of the compound noun is noun + noun = noun, its compound by *breg* (height) and *det* (sea).

if consulting the electronic dictionary, the first word *height* has the following explanation: “is the measurement of someone or something from head to foot or from base to top. The quality of begin tall or high. Elevation above (typically sea level). A high place or area. The most intense part or period of something or example of something: the height of bad manners” but in Albanian for the word *breg* is found: “që është pjesë rrip toke që kufizon në anë një rrjedhë uji, një det, një liqen etj. Anë toke që ndodhet buzë një sipërfaqeje uji”.ⁱⁱ

The second word has in the same dictionary this comment: “the expanse of salt water that covers most of them earth’s surface and surrounds its land masses”. A roughly definable area of this: “The black sea, etc.”, but in Albanian we have this explanation for the word *det*: “hapësirë shumë e madhe më ujë të kripur që zakonisht është e rrethuar me tokë jo nga të gjitha anët dhe që qëndron disi e veçuar, pjesa më e madhe e rruzullit tokësor, e mbuluar me ujë të kripur”.ⁱⁱⁱ

Both of them *breg* + *det* have creative the new word, with the new meaning *bregdet* – *beach* and this word beach has this meaning for example: “a pebbly or sandy shore at the edge of the sea or a lake. Bring on to a beach from the water, become or cause to become stranded on a beach”.

Another model studied on this research was the category “compound + affixes”, e.g. *bashkëkohës*, *zëvendës*, *kryengritje*, (*ngre kryet*) etc.

The Albanian words *zëvendës* and *kryengritje*, generated on this way, are presented on the figures below:

ⁱⁱ Fjalori elektornik shpjegues FESH 1.0.

ⁱⁱⁱ Ibidem, F.E.SH.

The third diagram - from the category "compound + affixes (suffixes)" – created a new word with a new meaning. The generative of the Albanian word /zëvendës/^{iv} we need to know the origin of the word. *Zëvendës*^v, comes from *zë-* verb or noun + *-vend* = noun and suffixes *-ës*, both of them are creating a new word with new meaning.

In the fourth diagram we have "noun + verb + suffix" - (*krye + ngrit -je* = *kryengritje*). The English language equivalents for this category of generative compounds are, for example, *housekeeper*^{vi} and *schoolbook*.

Figure 5

Figure 6

The generative study of English language has the origin on N. Chomsky’s book *Syntactic Structure*, 1957. After that, a lot of studies for English have been done, but not for Albanian.

The compound words *housekeeper* and *schoolbook* are made by “noun + noun + suffixes –er” and the word *schoolbook* is made by “noun + noun”. Both of them are creative and the new resulted words have a new meaning.

2. The synonymic and antonymic of compound nouns

In both Albanian and English, synonym and antonym compound words exist.

^{iv} [Sh. Millaku](http://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838), The Contrast of the Compound Words Between English and Albanian Language European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching, 2017, <http://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/838>

^v [S Millaku](http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/216), X Topanica, The Compound Nouns between English and Albanian Language, European Journal of Education Studies, 2016, <http://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/216>

^{vi} Also common in English is another type of verb-noun (or noun-verb) compound, in which an argument of the verb is [incorporated](#) into the verb, which is then usually turned into a [gerund](#), such as breastfeeding, finger-pointing, etc. The noun is often an instrumental complement. From these gerunds new verbs can be made: (a mother) breastfeeds (a child) and from them new compounds mother-child breastfeeding, etc. Here verbs describe what is done with an object or what a subject "does", in short, a new noun is formed, usually referring to something concrete, and the verb defines the action related to it: **Verb + Noun = Noun: draw + bridge = drawbridge**. A drawbridge is a bridge that can be inclined in order to allow ships to pass, or "drawn". Here, the noun is the direct object. hitman = a man who carries out "dirty jobs", or, who "hits". Here, the word as part of speech is the subject. Besides that, both segments can be related in other ways, i.e. the noun may stand for an adverb of place: walkway = people walk on the walkway. The usual rules apply to spelling. More examples: walkway (a way to walk on), divecenter (a place where one goes diving), runway (a strip of flat land where aircraft start or land ["run"]), filter-paper (paper used for filtering liquids or gases), driveway (a road leading to a garage or a building), payday (the day one receives his or her salary), paycheck (a check used for the payment of wages or salaries).

In Albanian, an example is *kokë dhe krye*^{vii}, which has built a lot of new words, all of them having a new meaning: *kokëderr*^{viii}, *kokëkungull*, *kokëmollë* or *krye-* e.g. *kryepriфт*, *kryenalt*^{ix}, *kryeqendrën*, *kryeviti*, *kryeqytet*, *kryepeshkop*, *kryeqytetas*, *kryeadministratat*, *kryeartikuj*, *kryeartikullit* etc.

In English language, this phenomena occurs the same way like in Albanian e.g. *homework*, *home-brew*, *home-coming*, *homeland*, *home-maker*, *homeopathy*, *homesickness* *home*, *homestead* or *house*, *house arrest*, *house owner*, *houseboat*, *housebreaker*, *housecoat*, *household*, *housekeeper*, *housemaid*, *houserom*, *housetop*, *housewife* etc.

The Albanian studies of J. Thomaj investigated this phenomenon and his opinion for synonym was:

“Nga aftësia për të krijuar fjalë të reja dhe për t’u lidhur me fjalë të reja në frazeologji, (p.sh. me të tjera fjalë) lidhet fjala kokë dhe të tjera kuptime merr ajo (kokëderr, kokëmish, kokëtul, kokëmadh, kokëdrejtues, kokë me rëndësi „i ditur”) dhe me të tjera fjalë lidhet e të tjera kuptime merr fjala krye (kryeqytet, kryeministër, kryeinxhinier, ...). Në fushën e përdorimit, këto dy sinonime nuk mund të zëvendësojnë gjithnjë njëra-tjetrin kështu nuk mund të themi krye me rëndësi, krye drejtuese etj., ashtu si nuk mund të themi kokëqytet e ndonjë tjetër. Pra, kokë dhe krye janë sinonime, po nuk i mbulojnë plotësisht njëri-tjetrin në përdorim”.^x

In this paper, has been concluded that between Albanian and English, words like *consummation*^{xi} are formed differently as compounds nouns.

^{vii} Shkelqim Millaku, The Genitive, IJALL, 2015, <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/IJLLIS/article/view/1218>

^{viii} Shkelqim Millaku, The Common and Proper Nouns Between Albanian and English, European Journal of Education Studies, 2017 - <http://edu.oapub.org/index.php/ejes/article/view/827>

^{ix} Shkelqim Millaku, The Function of Noun Phrases Between Albanian and English, <http://www.westeastinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/Shkelqim-Millaku.pdf>

^x Jani Thomaj, *Leksikologjia e gjuhës shqipe*, Tiranë, 1974, p.52-53.

^{xi} Compounding forms a word out of two or more root morphemes. Note that compounds are written in various ways in English: with a space between the elements, with a hyphen between the elements or simply with the two roots run together with no separation. The way the word is written does not affect its status as a compound. In Greek and Latin, on the other hand, roots do not typically stand alone. So compounds are composed of bound roots. Compounds formed in English from borrowed Latin and Greek morphemes preserve this characteristic. Examples include photograph, iatrogenic, and many thousands of other classical words. There are a number of subtypes of compounds, and they are not mutually exclusive. These words are compounded from two rhyming words. Examples: lovey-dovey chiller-killer etc. There are words that are formally very similar to rhyming compounds, but are not quite compounds in English because the second element is not really a word--it is just a nonsense item added to a root word to form a rhyme. Examples: higgledy-piggledy, tootsie-woodsy. This formation process is associated in English with child talk (and talk addressed to children). Examples: bunny-wunnie, Henny Penny, snuggly-wuggly etc. The most common type of word formation is the combination of two (or more) nouns in order to form a resulting noun: Noun + Noun = Noun. Examples: landmine, wallpaper, toothbrush. The first of the two compounds may be descriptive (i.e. tablecloth, a cloth with which to clean [or cloth] tables), or both compounds may create a whole new meaning altogether (i.e. railroad, which is not a "road" in the typical sense of the word.) It is also possible to form words whose components are equally important to or descriptive of its meaning, for example, a washer-dryer refers to an object combining two functions. There are, of course, many more different ways how compound nouns can be related to each other and how their new meanings can best be explained grammatically. In most cases, however, the nature of these compounds is self-explanatory, and their meanings are quite comprehensible even for those who encounter them for the first time. Note that compound nouns usually appear as two separate words, only

In Albanian language the compound words usually are created by two or more mining words. It is similarly, like in English, but in this language the phrase has function of the compound e.g. *alarm clock, traffic light^{xii}, parking meter, credit card, dining room, movie star*. In Albanian language it is impossible to form a compound in that way.

The next contrast is e.g. *son-in-law, edition-in-chief, man-of-war*; in Albanian usually they are simple words or in English they cannot be created as a compound with a preposition or a conjunctive.

These last examples emphasize the differences between the two languages.

References

- Bauer, Laurie. English Word-Formation, London, 1983.
Celce-Murcia, Mariana. The Grammar book, USA, 1999.
Celce-Murcia, Marianne. The Grammar book, USA, Heinlein, 1999.
Chomsky, Noam. Syntactic Structure, New York, 2002.
Christopher Pountain, M.F. Lang, Spanish Word Formation, London, 1990.
Doyle, Arthur Conan. The lost world and other thrilling tales, London, 2001.
Eddings, David. Magician's Gambit, London, 1983.
Fjalor i Gjuhës së Sotme Shqipe, Tiranë, 1980.
Fjalor i Termave të Gjuhësisë, Tiranë, 1975ë botuar nga Akademia e Shkencës e RPSH-INstituti i Gjuhësisë dhe i letërsisë, sektori i terminologjisë.
Fjalori i shqipes së sotme, Tiranë, 2002.
Henderickson, Robert. Word and phrase origins, New York, 1997.
Jokli, Norbert. Naim be Frashëri e pasunimi i gjuhës shqipe, Gjurmime albanologjike, seria shkencore filologjike II, 1972, Prishtinë, 1974.
Liz and John Soars, New Headway Advanced, Student's book, Oxford, 2003.
Master, Peter. English grammar and technical writing, Washington, 2004.
Millaku, Sh. (2009). Kontributi i Zellik Harris për gjuhësinë, IASH. Tetovë.
Millaku, Sh. (2015). Kërkime gjuhësore. Prizren.
Millaku, Sh. (2011). Studime gjuhësore I. Prishtinë.
Millaku, Sh. (2011). Strukturat sintaksore. Prishtinë.

those more commonly used, those found in every-day language, and usually compounds with no more than three syllables are found as one word. Hyphens (-) between the segments of a compound noun are absolutely exceptional. Examples: windowsill (the sill attached under a window), shop window (a shop's window), doorkey (a key for the door), bookpage (a page in a book), silverspoon (a spoon made of silver), waterpipe (a pipe that carries water), dockyard (a yard for docks), fireman (somebody who fights fire), wallpaper ("paper" one glues to walls), Independence Day (anniversary of the Declaration of Independence), office supply (goods for office use), water shortage (shortage of water), labour riot (employees rioting), television set (a set for watching television), headache (an aching head), snowfall (snow falling), answer phone (a phone that answers), air-conditioner (a machine conditioning air), gunfight (a fight carried out with guns).

^{xii} Shkelqim Millaku, The Function of Noun Phrases between Albanian and English, 2017,

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3051611

On-line references

- Shkelqim, M. The Function of Albanian and English Sentence, European Journal of English Language Teaching Available on-line at: Volume 2, Issue 3, 2017, Available on-line at <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/828>
- Dalina, K. The Comparative Syntax of Albanian, Durham, 1984, p. 85.
- Shkelqim, M. The contrast of Direct Object..., Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR) Vol-2, Issue-7, 2016 ISSN: 2454-1362, <http://www.onlinejournal.in>, <http://imperialjournals.com/index.php/IJIR/article/view/1320/1270>
- Shkelqim, M. The Indirect Object (IO) – Albanian and English, European Journal of Foreign Language Teaching, Volume 1, Issue 1, 2016, Available on-line at: <https://www.oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejfl/article/view/294/739>
- Shkelqim, M. Raporti i fjalive të thjeshta dhe kryefjalës ndërmjet shqipes dhe anglishtes, Available on-line at: https://www.academia.edu/29764804/Raporti_i_fjalive_te_thjeshta_dhe_kryefjales_ndermjet_shqipes_dhe_anglishtes
- Shkelqim, M. The Direct Object, Anglisticum... Volume 4, issue 1, 2015, e-ISSN: 1857-8187, p-ISSN: 1857-8179.
- Shkelqim, M. The Subject between Albanian and English Language, Anglisticum, April 2014, e-ISSN: 1857-8187, p-ISSN: 1857-8179, <http://www.anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/view/621/1450>
- Shkelqim, M. The Nominal Clauses of English and Albanian Language, Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research (IJIR) Vol-3, Issue-8, 2017 ISSN: 2454-1362, <http://www.onlinejournal.in> <http://www.imperialjournals.com/index.php/IJIR/article/viewFile/5472/5264>
- Flor, A. English syntactic structure. Cambridge, 1988, p. 143
- Nominal clause as prepositional complement: This raises the question as to whether we should abandon the plan. Nominal clause with /that/ e.g. That she is still alive is a consolation. "The nominative absolute is almost a clause. It consists of a noun phrase with a partial predicate: He smoked briefly, his eyes following a pattern of concrete blocks in the school building: Shkelqim Millaku, The Function Of Noun Phrases Between Albanian And English, The 2016 WEI International Academic Conference Proceedings Vienna, Austria, <http://www.westeastinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/Shkelqim-Millaku.pdf>

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